

**TYPES OF POVERTY MEASUREMENT, A SET OF MEASURES TO ALLEVIATE
POVERTY IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: *This article gives an economic and social definition of the term poverty, which is a sore point for the economies of countries, describes its manifestations, and outlines measures to alleviate poverty in Uzbekistan. Information was provided on the four main directions in the measurement of poverty, which of them are specific to the economy of Uzbekistan, and relevant proposals were formulated.*

Keywords: *poverty, poverty lines: nutrition-based poverty, international poverty, relative poverty and subjective poverty borders*

Аннотация: *В данной статье дается экономико-социальное определение термина бедность, являющегося большим вопросом для экономик стран, описываются его проявления, а также намечаются меры по смягчению бедности в Узбекистане. Была предоставлена информация по четырем основным направлениям в измерении бедности, какие из них специфичны для экономики Узбекистана, и сформулированы соответствующие предложения.*

Ключевые слова: *бедность, черта бедности: бедность по признаку питания, международная бедность, относительная бедность и границы субъективной бедности.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada mamlakatlar iqtisodiyotiga og'riqli nuqta hisoblanadigan kambag'allik terminiga iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy ta'rif berib, uning ko'rinishlarini tavsiflaydi hamda O'zbekiston miqyosida kambag'allikni yumshatishga doir tadbirlar shakllantirilgan. Kambag'allikni o'lchashdagi asosiy to'rtta yo'nalish haqida ma'lumot berilib, ulardan qaysilari O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xosligi aytib o'tilib, tegishli takliflar shakllantirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kambag'allik, kambag'allik chegaralari: oziqlanishga asoslangan kambag'allik, xalqaro kambag'allik, nisbiy kambag'allik va sub'yektiv kambag'allik chegaralari*

Poverty is a socio-economic concept and is usually an economic process that means that people do not have enough money to spend on basic necessities. Poverty is found in almost all countries of the world, both developed and developing. Because poverty has no positive effects, all countries try to avoid it. Globally, poverty criteria are divided into two categories.

The first and most important category is that the economic situation of these poor people is characterized by a negative indicator, namely, the lack of income for the subsistence level:

Income < Minimum living expenses

People who go through this process are described as "starving" or "dying." It is recommended to use this type of term for economically developing and underdeveloped countries.

The second category includes those who earn less than \$ 1.9 a day, which is not suitable for the general population, although the income from poverty assessment is sufficient to maintain housing, clothing, and life.

The non-economic interpretation of the concept of poverty may make it more difficult to understand the term. It includes poor health, low level of education or skills, inability to work or unwillingness to work. Due to the security nature of the term poverty, which has a tendency to be destructive and criminal, countries with high levels of poverty also have high crime rates, which in turn leads to various negative economic and political conditions. This attribute is hidden in many countries because of its economic backwardness. Due to differences of opinion among economists on who is poor and who is not poor, poverty is measured by the "poverty line", which is the highest in Uzbekistan. The most commonly used poverty line terms are:

1. Nutrition-based poverty line
2. International Poverty Limit
3. Relative poverty line
4. Subjective poverty line

Nutrition-Based Poverty Rate. Hunger is one of the manifestations of poverty. In this case, well-being is measured by the daily per capita caloric intake of the population and is compared to the amount of daily energy expenditure for this category of people. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) recommends setting an average daily energy consumption of 1,800 kilocalories. This figure can vary depending on age, gender and level of human activity. Other forms of nutrient deficiencies, such as protein or certain micronutrients called "hidden hunger," may also be limited. In this case, the overall level of poverty can be determined from the recommended minimum level.

International Poverty Limit. This limit is used by the World Bank for international comparisons. The extreme poverty line is set at \$ 1 per day at purchasing power parity, and the poverty line is set at \$ 2 per day. The poverty line has recently been raised to \$ 1.25 and \$ 2.5, respectively. Currently, 15 of the world's poorest countries use these poverty lines. However, at present, other limits of poverty are applied, taking into account the specific characteristics and stages of development of different countries. In particular, it is recommended to use the low-income level of \$ 3.2 per day for low-income countries and \$ 5.5 per day for high-income countries.

Relative poverty line. Poverty is not only an absolute but also a relative concept. People may have a subjective assessment of their level of consumption compared to other people in the appropriate control group. Because of this notion of relative deprivation, people focus on their personal income or consumption levels relative to the average in their country or community. The relative poverty line can also be interpreted as the cost of social integration required for decent participation in normal socio-economic activities. The use of the relative poverty line is common in European countries. In this case, the poor are considered to be the 25% of the lowest consumers in the country.

Subjective poverty line. We can say that poverty is not only an absolute or relative standard, but also a perception. In this case, it is determined what amount of expenses households consider as the minimum level, and this is compared with the level of their actual costs. Thus, the share of those whose current expenditures fall below the declared subjective minimum is considered the poverty rate. However, the level of poverty here can often be interpreted differently depending on how the question is asked.

In Uzbekistan, only the first two methods are used to measure poverty. The results of the nutrition-based approach show that the poverty rate is 11.4%. Based on the results of the second approach, the poverty rate is 36.6% for the \$ 5.5 limit per day and 9.6% for the \$ 3.6 limit. According to the World Bank, the highest levels of poverty are in Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, Andijan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In recent years, significant progress has been made in creating a public database that can be used to study the level of poverty. They allow us to describe poverty, its factors, as well as many hypotheses about the impact of specific programs and political reforms on poverty. For example, by comparing the characteristics of poor and non-poor people or households, it is possible to determine the cause of poverty and set clear parameters for combating it.

A clearer picture of poverty in Uzbekistan is defined by the content of key measures and recommendations to combat it. According to research in this area, a low-income family consists of 7 people, the average age of the head of the family is over 50 years and he has no higher education. In particular, 11% of the heads of low-income families are unemployed, 93% do not have higher education and only 24% have secondary special education. 43% of low-income households do not have a permanent job. 93% are not connected to the central heating system, 96% are not connected to the central sewage system and 66% are not connected to the central water supply.

In conclusion, poverty has the appearance of complex negative socio-political characteristics. In order to prevent poverty in Uzbekistan, it is important to focus on decent education and skills, and to take measures to encourage employment. Recommendations on combating poverty are based on the characteristics of low-

income households, socio-economic barriers to participation in society and promising areas of development, as well as policy at the macroeconomic and micro levels.

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